

Machine Learning and its Applications in Astronomy

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March 30, 2025

Abstract

The primary goal of this project is to differentiate between stars and non-star objects in the night sky through machine learning techniques. The night sky contains a variety of celestial objects such as galaxies, active galactic nuclei (AGN), and quasi-stellar objects (quasars). Galaxies are vast systems comprising stars, dust, and often supermassive black holes. Despite their enormous sizes, they appear minuscule from Earth due to their immense distance. Accurately classifying these objects is crucial to prevent confusion between stars and non-stellar entities, which can compromise astronomical data and analysis. Astronomical observations, typically carried out using telescopes, yield massive datasets containing information about the observed celestial bodies. In the case of stars, relevant attributes include luminosity, radius, absolute magnitude, color, and more. Analyzing this information manually is time-consuming and prone to errors. Machine learning offers a solution by enabling computers to learn patterns from data and make reliable classifications. By examining features across the electromagnetic spectrum, machine learning models can predict the likelihood of an object being a star or a non-star with significant accuracy. This project presents a comparative study of three machine learning algorithms used for stellar classification: Logistic Regression, KNN and Random Forest. Each model is evaluated based on its performance and efficiency in classifying celestial objects. The results highlight how machine learning can not only streamline astronomical classification but also enhance accuracy, making it an invaluable tool in modern astronomy.

Keywords: Star, Galaxies, Quasars, Machine Learning, Logistic Regression, KNN, Random Forest

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1 Introduction

For a millennia, humans have been fascinated by the cosmos and the mysteries lying underneath. With the desire of humans, to explore the unknown, we have made groundbreaking discoveries and remarkable achievements. With the advancements in the field of astronomy, new instruments are developed, including advanced telescopes and photometers. Moreover, advent of new technologies led us to develop new astronomical surveys, that uses advanced telescopes and equipment like photometers to obtain useful information (mostly photo-metric information) about the objects in the sky. In 1989, HIPPARCOS Mission was launched by the European Space Agency that catalogued 118,218 stars in the universe and was functional till 1994. The Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) is an important sky survey that started recently and collects useful photometric data of stars, galaxies and QSOs in the universe. With the advent of advanced Astronomical surveys, large amount of data about Astronomical objects started getting collected in the databases. For understanding the physics of these objects, it was necessary to analyse the data. However, analyzing such a large volume of data proved to be a challenging task for scientists, and there was a constant need to drift away from traditional methods of data analysis and seek new methods. Machine Learning algorithms like Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbours became very important tools for analysis. This reports mainly centres around a classification problem- classification of stars, galaxies and quasars from the Data Release 18 of SDSS V.

In the first section, we have studied the data in detail and a description of data has been put forward for better understanding of the various features under study in SDSS mission. In the preceeding section, we have given a description of how the data has been preprocessed for application to the Machine Learning Models- how the features were chosen for the classification, how was the imbalance in the dataset removed and how was the data encoded for classification. The next section provides us with a description of the Machine Learning Algorithms that we have used for the classification. Then, we have provided the results of the classification, and a comparative study of the results is done using the confusion matrices, heatmaps, the recall scores and the run time for each algorithm.

2 Preprocessing of data

The dataset used for this research work has been downloaded from the SDSS website (<http://cas.sdss.org/dr18/>). The dataset downloaded, however, has to be modified to be made suitable for our usage. The dataset consists of photometric data (like p.run, p.rerun, p.camcol, p.field) and spectroscopic data (like s.specobjid, s.class, s.plate, s.mjd). We change the output format of the dataset from html to csv and download it. After downloading it, we delete the heading and the 'table' row so that only the main data remains to be analysed. Finally, we export the file in csv format as our dataset is now ready to be utilised.

In our venture to explore the Machine Learning models for the data analysis, our focus has always been directed towards a subset of parameters, namely “u”, “g”, “r”, “i”, “z”, “redshift”, “plate” and “class”. This choice has been done after carefully considering and omitting some parameters, including “objid”, “ra”, “dec”, “run”, “rerun”, “camcol”, “field”, “fiberid” and “specobjid”. However, these variables were not arbitrarily excluded from our study; rather, the nature of the research objectives, directed us to exclude these variables. Variables “ra” and “dec” represent the spatial coordinates and “objid” is the unique identifier for the astronomical object and these are not relevant to our investigation, which is primarily concerned towards the classification of the astronomical objects based on spectroscopic data. Similarly, the parameters “run”, “rerun”, “camcol” and “field” are related to the features of the setup required for the observation and do not directly contribute to spectroscopic features. “fiberid” and “specobjid” are primarily concerned with technical aspects of collection of data and are not directly relevant to our investigation. “mjd” or Modern Julian Date may be an important parameter for analysis when time comes into consideration, but it is not quite relevant here, making its omission acceptable.

Target Variable: **class** (the stellar body that needs to be identified). To work with our dataset, we encode it so that the string variables (the class of the star) are converted to integer values. We achieve this by using the ‘LabelEncoder’ method from the ‘sklearn.preprocessing’ package made available by Python.

3 Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression is a Machine Learning method that is used in Supervised Learning for Classification problems. It is used when the goal is to predict the probability of an instance belonging to a given class. It is a statistical algorithm, which analyses the relationship between a set of independent variables and the dependent binary variables. It is a powerful tool for decision-making and can be extended to multi-class problems like stellar classification.

Figure 1: Sigmoid Curve

$$\phi(z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}}$$

The graph of the Logistic Regression mechanism looks like the S-shaped curve above which represents the Sigmoid function. This nature of the Sigmoid function makes it suitable for modelling the probability of binary outcomes.

Data Processing

Since we are using the Logistic Regression Machine Learning method in this case, which is a Supervised Learning method, which implies that our ML model has to be first familiarised with a set of data whose outcome is known to us before it can analyse unknown data.

To divide the dataset into the training and testing datasets, we first decide our target variable, which in this case, is 'Class'. Then we select which features among all given in the dataset we wish to analyse and take into account while training our model. It is important that the features we choose have a direct correlation with evaluating the 'Class'. In this case, we have considered features like ultraviolet radiation, gamma radiation, infrared radiation, redshift, etc.

We divide our existing dataset into two parts: the training dataset and the testing dataset in the ratio 3 : 1. As the names suggest, one of these sets of data will be used to train our Logistic Regression model and the other set of data will be used to test and score it. For this, we use the method 'train_test_split' from the sklearn package.

Algorithm and Implementation

As stellar classification is a multiclass classification to which we have extended our Logistic Regression model, for each class, we build a logistic regression to find the probability the observation belongs to that class and for each data point, we predict the class with the highest probability.

In this case, the algorithm takes into account each feature, say, ultraviolet radiation, and evaluates the probability of the ultraviolet radiation belonging to a star, a galaxy or a quasi-stellar object. The algorithm continues this mechanism for every feature and finally gives an outcome based on the highest probability of the data belonging to a certain class. The Logistic Regression model does not answer which class the given data belongs to; it answers whether the given data belongs to a specific class.

Interpretation of the result obtained

Accuracy score in machine learning is an evaluation metric that measures the number of correct predictions made by a model in relation to the total number of predictions made. We calculate it by dividing the number of correct predictions by the total number of predictions, or in this case by using the 'LogisticRegression.score' method from the 'sklearn' package.

The Accuracy score of this model for stellar classification is 0.8422 , which is essentially, 84.22%.

An accuracy score between 70% and 90% is not ideal but is realistic. Many a times, an accuracy score of above 90% indicates that the data is over-fitted and works really well for only the given set of data and not with any other set of data. A score between 80% and 90% indicates that the model works well with most data.

A confusion matrix is a table that represents the exact number of outcomes predicted correctly and incorrectly for each class. A heat map of the confusion matrix is a visual representation of the same.

The confusion matrix for this model is

```
array([[11501, 33, 1338],
       [ 253, 2317, 94],
       [ 1882, 345, 7237]], dtype=int64)
```

Its corresponding heat map is

Figure 2: Heat Map for Classification using Logistic Regression

Confusion Matrix for Stellar Classification model using Logistic Regression
 As it can be seen, the y -axis represents the Actual Diagnosis and the x -axis represents the Predicted Diagnosis. Hence, the diagonals represent the number of times the model predicted the class of the data correctly.

In row 1, we can see that the total number of times data belonging to the class 'Galaxy' tested was 12,872, out of which 11,501 times the model did predict the data belongs to the class 'Galaxy', 33 times it predicted that it belonged to the class 'Star' and 1338 times it predicted that it belonged to the class 'QSO' (Quasi-stellar object).

A model with a good accuracy score will have a confusion matrix that has maximum values in its diagonals and minimum to no values in any other grid. As it is seen above, the confusion matrix does have maximum values in its diagonals. From the above confusion matrix, it can also be inferred that this Logistic Regression model often confuses QSOs and Galaxies and is decently accurate at recognizing stars.

4 KNN

The K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm is a supervised machine learning method employed to tackle classification and regression problems. It is a versatile algorithm with several advantages, including its simplicity, ease of implementation, and lack of assumptions about the underlying data distribution. KNN works on the idea that comparable items are likely to be close to each other in the feature space. But, it can be computationally expensive, particularly for big datasets, because it involves calculating distances between the new point and all points in the training set.

Here's how the KNN algorithm operates:

- **Training:** During the training phase, the algorithm simply memorises the feature vectors and their class labels.
- **Prediction:** When a new data point is introduced, the algorithm computes its distance from all other points in the training dataset using a distance metric, usually Euclidean distance.
- **Selection:** Using the calculated distances, the algorithm selects the k-nearest neighbours (k is a user-defined parameter).
- **Voting:** For classification tasks, KNN uses a majority vote among the k-nearest neighbours to assign a class label to a new data point based on the most prevalent class among its neighbours.

Data Processing

We use pandas to load the data set. Before proceeding further the dataset is split into train and test in the ratio 3:1.

What is parameter tuning?

KNN algorithm is based on feature similarity. choosing right value of k is a process called *parameter tuning*.

To choose a value of k:

- Take \sqrt{n} , where n is the total number of data points
- Odd value of n is selected to avoid confusion between two classes of data

We calculate euclidian distance of unknown data point from all the points in the dataset. Then we find the nearest neighbours for a chosen value of k.

In order to determine the most prevalent classification for these entries, we choose the k entries in our database that are most similar to the new sample. This is the category we assign to the recently added entries.

Figure 3: Heat Map for Classification using KNN

Advantages and disadvantages of KNN in stellar classification

Advantages

1. **Simplicity:** KNN is straightforward to understand and implement. It doesn't require complex assumptions about the underlying data distribution.
2. **No Training Phase:** KNN doesn't have a training phase. It stores all the training data and classifies new instances based on their similarity to existing data points.
3. **Adaptability:** KNN can adapt to changes in data patterns easily. As new data points are added to the dataset, the algorithm can quickly adjust its decision boundaries.
4. **Non-parametric:** KNN is non-parametric, meaning it doesn't assume anything about the underlying data distribution. This makes it suitable for scenarios where the data distribution is unknown or complex.
5. **Suitable for Multi-Class Classification:** KNN naturally supports multi-class classification without needing modifications to the algorithm.
6. **Works well with Small Datasets:** KNN performs well when the dataset is small or the feature space is not too large.

Disadvantages

1. **Computational Complexity:** The main disadvantage of KNN is its computational complexity during classification. As the size of the dataset grows, the time taken to classify new instances also increases since it requires computing distances to all data points.

2. Sensitive to Irrelevant Features: KNN considers all features equally, which can be a disadvantage when dealing with datasets containing irrelevant or noisy features.
3. Requires Feature Scaling: KNN's performance can be sensitive to the scale of features. Therefore, it's important to scale features appropriately before applying KNN.
4. Decision Boundary Sensitivity: KNN's decision boundary can be sensitive to the value of 'k' and the choice of distance metric, which may lead to suboptimal results in some cases.

5 Decision tree

Decision Trees are a versatile tool in the field of machine learning used for both classification and regression tasks. They represent a tree-like structure where each node which is simple decision or condition on individual or combined features. Each possible outcome of a decision corresponds to an outgoing branch of the node, which leads to another node representing another decision and so on. The process continues until a final node, called a leaf, is reached. Building up a DT is a supervised learning process.

Random forest(RF) is an ensemble learning method that constructs a multiple decision trees during training(Breiman 2001). The idea behind RF is to combine the decisions of several such trees to improve upon the decision of a single over-trained tree. Taking a majority-vote over the decision of all the trees, helps to reduce overfitting and increase accuracy (Breiman 2001).

Data Processing

We are using sklearn model selection package and it's class train-test split to split our data into the training and testing module in the ratio of 3:1.

Construction:

CART (Classification and Regression Trees):We are using the CART algorithm (Breiman et al. 1984). It is similar to C4.5 in the process of tree construction, but while C4.5 uses information gain to select the best test to be performed on a node, CART uses the Giniindex.It is a versatile algorithm that can be used for both classification and regression tasks. It builds binary trees and partitions the data into subsets based on feature thresholds, aiming to minimize impurity.

Algorithm for CART:

(4) shows a graphical representation of a simple DT constructed with 75,000 randomly chosen SDSS objects having spectroscopic data. At its topmost node

Figure 4: Decision Tree Data Structure

(the root node), the tree may branches out into two depending on whether the value of the feature "redshift" is less than or greater than equal to 0.002 . Either of these branches may lead to a child node which may test the same feature, a different one, or a combination. The path from the root node to a leaf corresponds to a single classification rule. The DT is built node by node based on a data set where the target are already known. This data set is formed from training examples, each consisting of a combination of feature that leads to a target. The process starts with all training examples in the root node of the tree. A feature is chosen for testing in the node. Then, for each possible result of the test a branch is created and the data set is split into subsets of training examples that have the features specified by the branch. A child node is created for each branch and the process is repeated, splitting each subset into new subsets. Child nodes are created recursively until all training examples have the same target or all the training examples at the node have the same values for all the features. Each leaf node gives either a classification, a set of classifications, or a probability distribution over all possible classifications. The CART uses measures like Gini impurity to evaluate the impurity or randomness of a dataset. The feature that results in the greatest reduction in impurity after the split is chosen as the splitting feature. The goal is to maximize the information gain or minimize impurity at each step.

In the context of decision trees, "impurity" refers to the lack of uniformity or homogeneity in a dataset. It measures how mixed the classes or values are within a given split are.

Gini impurity is a measure used in decision tree algorithms, such as CART (Classification and Regression Trees), to evaluate the impurity or the lack of homogeneity in a dataset during the process of determining the best feature for splitting.

Gini impurity is calculated by considering how often a randomly chosen element from the dataset would be incorrectly classified if it were randomly labeled according to the distribution of labels in the subset. It's expressed as a value between 0 and 0.5 , where:

A Gini impurity of 0 represents a pure dataset where all elements belong

to the same class. A Gini impurity of 0.5 represents the maximum impurity or maximum uncertainty, where the classes are evenly distributed within the subset.

The formula for Gini impurity is:

$$\text{Gini Impurity} = 1 - \sum (\text{probability of class } i)^2$$

Hyperparameters Selection: To Avoid overfitting, we are setting the max depth of the tree to be 5 because after the accuracy of the leaf nodes get saturated.

Score: 0.98824 + / - 0.004

array:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} 12742 & 132 & 14 \\ 132 & 2543 & 0 \\ 16 & 0 & 9421 \end{Bmatrix} [\text{dtype64}]$$

Figure 5: Heat Map for Classification using Decision Tree

Key characteristics of CART

Key characteristics of the CART algorithm include:

- **Binary Tree Structure:** CART creates a binary tree where each node has two child nodes. This structure simplifies decision-making and enhances interpretability.
- **Splitting Criteria:** The algorithm selects features and creates splits that reduce impurity within the resulting nodes. For classification, it uses measures like Gini impurity or entropy to determine the best feature and threshold for splitting. For regression tasks, it uses variance reduction to determine the splitting.
- **Recursive Partitioning:** It recursively partitions the dataset based on the selected features to create subsets that are as homogeneous as possible with respect to the target variable.

- Stopping Criteria: The tree-building process stops when a predefined stopping criterion is met, such as reaching a maximum depth, having a minimum number of samples in a node, or when no further split can significantly reduce impurity.
- Handling Categorical and Numerical Data: CART can handle both categorical and numerical attributes.
- Scalability: It can handle large datasets and is relatively fast in both training and prediction phases.
- Ensemble Methods: CART serves as the basis for ensemble methods like Random Forest, where multiple decision trees are built to increase accuracy and reduce overfitting.

Random Forest

Figure 6: Random Forest Data Structure

In (6), we illustrate the decision making process of a simple RF algorithm, where the decisions of 3 DT trees are combined to improve upon the decision of a single over-trained tree. In the sklearn algorithm, the dataset of 75000 is divided into batch of 20 random data subsets, then a DT is built for each subset. Now when all the 20 DTs are trained and they will all come up with different decisions. Now a majority vote of all decision given by the different DTs are taken to make the prediction. Hyperparameters Selection: The max features parameter specifies the number of features to consider when looking for the best split. We have used max features='log2' which represents that the number of features considered for each split is the base-2 logarithm of the total number of features. The n-estimators parameter specifies the number of DTs to formed out of the whole dataset. We have selected the value to be 20, to reduce overfitting. Score: 0.99186 +/- 0.0007

Figure 7: Heat Map for Classification using Random Forest

Confusion Matrix:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ccc} 12835 & 34 & 19 \\ 141 & 2532 & 2 \\ 17 & 0 & 9420 \end{array} \right\} [\text{dtype64}]$$

Key characteristics of the Random forest algorithm:

Key characteristics of the Random forest algorithm include:

- **Ensemble of Decision Trees:** Random Forest combines the predictions of multiple decision trees, reducing overfitting and improving classification.
- **Feature Importance:** Random Forest provides a measure of feature importance, allowing astronomers to identify which features (e.g., photometric measurements) are most influential in classifying celestial objects.
- **Tolerance to Noise:** Random Forest is robust to noisy data, a common challenge in astronomical observations.
- **Scalability:** The algorithm is scalable, making it suitable for analyzing the massive volume of data from the SDSS.

Advantages:

Interpretability: Decision Trees are easy to interpret and visualize. They mimic human decision-making, making them a popular choice for comprehensibility. **Handling Non-Linearity:** They can handle both numerical and categorical data and can capture non-linear relationships. **Feature Selection:** They automatically select the most relevant features. **Fast Prediction:** They have logarithmic time complexity for prediction.

Limitations:

Overfitting: It's important to handle potential overfitting issues by tuning parameters like maximum depth, minimum samples for a split, or utilizing ensemble methods.

ble methods when using the CART algorithm. Instability: Small variations in the data can result in a completely different tree structure. Bias towards features with more levels: Attributes with more levels will be selected more often by the algorithm.

6 Conclusion

Logistic Regression is a powerful algorithm for predicting binary outcomes, however, its outcomes aren't exceedingly accurate when it comes to multiclass classifications like stellar classification.

While KNN's simplicity is appealing, it's not the best fit for stellar classification. Stellar data often has many dimensions, and KNN struggles in these high-dimensional spaces. Analyzing massive datasets with KNN becomes slow and computationally expensive. Additionally, stellar data might have irrelevant features that can mislead KNN. Unlike some other algorithms, KNN also doesn't explain its reasoning, making it difficult to understand why a star is classified a certain way. For stellar classification, algorithms like SVMs, decision trees, random forests, or even deep learning models are better choices due to their ability to handle high dimensions, resist irrelevant features, offer interpretability, and perform well with large datasets.

Decision Trees are powerful tools in the realm of machine learning due to their simplicity, interpretability, and versatility. However, their performance can be enhanced by using ensemble methods like Random Forests, which mitigate the overfitting and less impurity gain limitations of individual Decision Trees. By using random forest in our classification of SDSS data there is a significant less number of galaxies which are predicted as Quasars. Splitting of dataset can differ the outcome score by $+/- 0.0004$.

From an analysis of recall scores and run times, it is clear that Random Forest shows the highest recall score, followed by Decision Tree, KNN and Logistic Regression. Although Random Forest show high recall scores, it takes more than 30 minutes for obtaining the results, whereas, KNN and Logistic Regression has lower recall scores and takes longer time to learn. Decision Tree algorithm seem to be the best option among the Machine learning algorithms for such classification problems, owing to its high recall score and least run time. However, it must also be kept in mind that the Decision Tree algorithm has a downside in the form of overfitting the data. To conclude, it is best that we opt for Random Forest Classifier, owing to their reliability for such classification problems.

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